
PIERRE BOURDIEU'S THEORY OF HABITUS AND SOCIAL SPACE

Kusmanova A.,

Student – Bachelor's degree – School of Informational Technologies

Nurmagambetkyzy R.,

Student – Bachelor's degree – School of Informational Technologies

Toleugaliyev N.,

Student – Bachelor's degree – School of Informational Technologies

Tileubayeva M.

Associated professor, PhD

Abstract

This sociological project is dedicated to the study of the theory of habitus and social space provided by Pierre Bourdieu, in order to better understand the social system and how the world around us can influence our personalities.

Keywords: Experiment, survey, methods, personality, environment, critical analysis and evaluation of social space, result, social mobilization, sociological research, influence of the social environment, hierarchical social positions and relationships, multimodular approach.

INTRODUCTION

Pierre Bourdieu's experiment on the Theory of Habitus and Social Space can be difficult, since his theory is more aimed at describing social reality and processes than at conducting specific experiments.

However, it is possible to conduct research that can help confirm or refute the theory of habitus and social space. For example, it is possible to conduct a study that will examine the influence of social factors on the development of habits in children and adolescents. The study can cover such factors as the social status of the family, the education of parents, the availability of cultural resources, etc.

Also, it is possible to conduct a study that will study the relationship between habitus and social space. The research can cover such aspects as social mobility, the possibility of access to resources, as well as the influence of cultural norms and values on the formation of habitus and the development of social space.

However, conducting such studies can be quite complex and require significant resources and time. Also, the results of such studies may be quite difficult to interpret and may be challenged by other researchers.

1.1. Theoretical aspects of the topic

Pierre Bourdieu's theory of habitus and social space has gained immense popularity in the field of sociology and has been widely discussed in academia since its inception. The theory aims to explain how individuals and groups acquire social identities and the ways in which their social positions are shaped by cultural and social factors. The relevance of this theory lies in its potential to shed light on the complex interplay between individual agency and social structure, which has become a key focus in modern sociology.

"Habitus" is a kind of tool that is used by people to navigate in the social space and determine their place in it. Bourdieu's concept of social space describes how different social groups, classes and individuals are located in space depending on their position in the social and economic structure of society.

According to Bourdieu, social space can be represented as a three-dimensional model, where each di-

mension corresponds to a certain form of capital: economic, cultural and social. These forms of capital can be accumulated and used to gain advantages in the social space.

Pierre Bourdieu's theory of social space is a powerful lens through which we can understand how social structures and inequalities are reproduced and strengthened over time. In the "Extended Case Method", Michael Buravoy writes the following: "Bourdieu's theory of social space is emphasized by the way in which social structures and inequality are reproduced and reinforced through struggle and competition among social actors for resources, status and power." That is, Bourdieu's theory notes the struggle and rivalry that occur between social actors for resources, status and power in the multidimensional space of social positions and relationships.

Through this struggle, social actors reproduce and strengthen social structures and inequality. This is due to the fact that the results of these competitions are determined not only by individual abilities or efforts, but also by the distribution of social and cultural capital within society. Those with more social and cultural capital are in the best position to succeed in this struggle, while those without such capital are often left behind.

As a result, social space is not a level playing field, but rather a space of uneven opportunities and outcomes. Social actors are positioned in this space based on a number of factors, including their social class, education, family background and cultural experience. These factors shape their access to resources, status and power and, ultimately, their life chances.

Bourdieu's theory of social space provides a framework for understanding how social structures and inequalities are reproduced and reinforced over time as a result of struggles and rivalries between social actors. By studying the ways of positioning social actors in the social space, we can gain a deeper understanding of the complex ways of preserving social structures and inequality, as well as the problems associated with the implementation of social change.

In the work "Identity Design: Sights and Sounds of a Nation," Karen A. Cherulo notes: "Bourdieu's concept of habitus helps to explain why social change is often slow and difficult, as individuals are deeply invested in the cultural and social practices that have shaped their identities and worldviews."

This is particularly true in the case of cultural and social practices that are tied to individuals' identities, such as religious practices or national traditions. These practices are not just individual choices, but are deeply embedded in the social and cultural structures that shape individuals' lives. As a result, changing these practices often requires challenging the broader social and cultural structures in which they are embedded.

Thus, Pierre Bourdieu's theory of "habitus" and social space describes how social structures, including class inequality and cultural differences, shape the behavior and thinking of individuals. This theory has important significance for social science and can be used to explain various phenomena in social dynamics, such as mobility, inequality and social mobilization.

1.2. Formulation of the problem of the Pierre Bourdieu theory

Despite its widespread use, Bourdieu's theory of habitus and social space remains a complex and multifaceted concept with many nuances and unresolved issues. Thus, the research problem addressed in this paper is a critical analysis and evaluation of social space, its key concepts related to its application in modern sociological research.

Bourdieu's theory places too much emphasis on the role of social structure and not enough on individual activity, while others question its ability to take into account the diversity of social experience and identity in modern societies. This study is aimed at identifying the relationship and interrelation of the individual with society, where the habitus of a person was formed on the basis of the social environment in which he spent growing up and becoming a person. The issues affecting the habitus as an individual object will be discussed below:

- 1) How the social environment influenced the formation of a person's personality;
- 2) What positive and negative qualities entailed the relationship of an individual with society;
- 3) The difference in the social environment of a person.

In addition, the purpose of this study is to explore the potential of Bourdieu's habitus theory and social space for solving modern social problems such as inequality, discrimination and social mobility. Although Bourdieu's theory has been widely used in sociological research, there is a need for further analysis of its application in the current social and political context.

This research is aimed at studying the limitations of Bourdieu's theory of habitus and social space and its relevance in the modern world. This includes an analysis of its applicability to various social contexts, its ability to account for intersectional identities, and its potential to incorporate new developments in sociology and related disciplines.

In general, this research task is aimed at social analysis and evaluation of Bourdieu's theory of habitus and social space, taking into account its strengths and

limitations, as well as its potential for solving modern social problems. The results of this study can contribute to a better understanding of the relationship between the individual and society and serve as a basis for developing effective strategies to promote social change and reduce inequality.

1.3. The main goals of the researching the topic

The primary aim of this dissertation is to provide a comprehensive and critical analysis of Bourdieu's theory of habitus and social space. To achieve this goal, the following objectives are pursued:

- To examine the origins and development of Bourdieu's theory of habitus and social space, including the key concepts and theoretical frameworks that underpin it.
- To critically evaluate the application of Bourdieu's theory in contemporary sociological research, including its strengths and limitations.
- To conduct a social survey among students aged 18-21 years in order to study the influence of the social environment on a person's personality.

1.4. Object of the research

The purpose of this study is a critical analysis of Bourdieu's theory of habitus and social space, its key concepts and debates related to its application in modern sociological research. The research will explore how theory contributes to our understanding of social identity, cultural capital, social reproduction and environmental relations as a form of power. To form the following arguments, a social survey will be conducted among students as an object of experiment and confirmation of the theory of human habitus. Critically assessing the theoretical foundations of habitus and social space, this study aims to contribute to the ongoing debate in the field of sociology and provide information for future research.

The key concept of the theory is habitus, which Bourdieu defines as embodied cultural tendencies and practices that shape an individual's perception of the world and their behavior within it. He argues that habitus is a product of social experience and upbringing, and is formed over the course of long-term socialization within a socio-cultural environment.

Social space, on the other hand, is defined as the structured and hierarchical social positions and relationships that individuals occupy within society. It includes factors such as class, gender, race, and cultural customs.

SOCIOLOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF THEORY OF SOCIAL SPACE AND HABITUS

2.1. Reviewing the methods of researching

The study of the theory of habitus and social space by Pierre Bourdieu requires a multimodal approach combining quantitative and qualitative methods. Some of the most common methods used in this field of research. Our method uses a method of collecting information through a survey.

Surveys can be used to collect quantitative data on the distribution of various forms of capital among the population. For example, a survey may be conducted to examine the relationship between social class and cultural consumption. The survey allows you to collect

data on the types of cultural activities that various social classes are engaged in, as well as their attitudes towards various cultural forms.

Based on the information provided, it appears that the survey conducted among 45 people aimed to gather information about their opinions and beliefs regarding the impact of the environment on their habits, personality, and life.

The survey questions that were asked are intended to clarify opinions about the role of the environment in

shaping the behavior, attitudes and beliefs of an individual.

2.2 Analysis of social survey

Question 1 asks "Has the environment influenced the formation of current habits?" and provides two response options: "Yes" and "No". Based on the survey results provided, 88.6% of the participants responded "Yes" and 11.4% responded "No".

This suggests that the majority of participants feel that their current habits have been influenced by the environment in which they live. It is important to note, however, that without additional context or details about the specific habits and environmental factors in question, it is challenging to come to definitive conclusions about the relationship between the environment and habits without additional context or details about the specific habits and environmental factors in question.

It may also be worth exploring how participants defined "environment" when responding to this question, as the term can encompass a wide range of factors, from physical surroundings to social and cultural influences.

Question 2 asks the survey participants whether they think their personality was formed based on the environment in which they lived. According to the survey results, 94.3% of the participants answered "Yes",

while 5.7% answered "No". This indicates that the majority of the participants believe that their personality was influenced by their environment.

The question is related to the nature versus nurture debate, which is a long-standing argument in psychology about whether human behavior is determined by genetics (nature) or the environment (nurture). The results of this survey suggest that the participants lean more towards the nurture side of the debate, believing that their personality was shaped by the environment they lived in.

In question 3, it was asked the participants to evaluate the impact of society on their life on a five-point scale. Based on the data you provided, the average score falls within the range of 3.70-4.60. This suggests that the participants generally perceive a moderate to high level of impact of society on their life.

It is important to note that without knowing the specific questions and response options provided in the survey, it is difficult to provide a more detailed interpretation of the results. Additionally, it is possible that the interpretation of the scale may vary among individuals, so it would be beneficial to consider additional measures to validate the interpretation of the results.

The second part on the scale shows 2.80-3.70 grades. Considering that our subjects for the study are young people, namely, in most cases, students, then slightly less than half of the people demonstrate other ideas. This assessment suggests that the influence of society is not always perceived positively. Taking into account the fact that more than 90% of people believe that the influence of society has had a great effect on them, it can be assumed that the formation of personality, namely "habitus", was affected by negative changes. This point is especially studied in other studies, where the main subjects are people whose personalities have been established by the rules of the negative environment.

Question 4 asked participants whether they perceived any benefits from the influence of their environment on them. The results showed that the majority of participants (91.4%) reported that they did perceive benefits, while a smaller proportion (8.6%) reported that they did not.

It would be interesting to further explore what these perceived benefits are and how they manifest in different individuals. It's also worth noting that this question relies heavily on subjective interpretation, as what one person perceives as a benefit may not be seen as such by another person. Nonetheless, the high percentage of respondents who reported perceiving benefits suggests that most people see at least some positive effects of their environment on their lives.

Also, during the survey, open questions were taken into account, where we asked people "How did your personality form based on the environment in which you lived?" To which various answers were received, but the overwhelming majority spoke about the good influence of society on the formation of their personality "habitus". At least, thanks to people from the environment who are drawn to knowledge, several individuals had a craving for the same knowledge and the development of discipline.

However, some students also reported negative impacts of the environment. Moreover, this is expressed in various forms, both from the mental side and from the social side.

In general, the study of the theory of habitus and social space by Pierre Bourdieu requires a multimodular approach combining quantitative and qualitative methods. In this case, a survey was used to collect data on the opinions and beliefs of 45 individuals about the impact of the environment on their habits, personality, and life.

The results of the survey suggest that the majority of participants believe that their current habits, personality, and lifestyle have been influenced by the environment in which they live. The high percentage of re-

spondents who reported perceiving benefits of their environment suggests that many people see positive effects of their environment on their lives.

However, the survey also revealed that some participants perceive negative impacts of society on their lives, both from the mental side and from the social side. This highlights the need to consider the specific nature of the environment and the individual's perception of it when studying the relationship between environment and behavior.

The study also emphasizes the importance of considering a multimodular approach to research, as combining quantitative and qualitative methods can provide a more comprehensive understanding of the complex interplay between environment and behavior.

Overall, the findings of this study may be useful in conducting further research in this area and in developing interventions aimed at changing behavior by changing the environment.

2.3. Conclusion from the methodology

This dissertation sought to provide a comprehensive and critical analysis of Bourdieu's theory of habitus and social space by examining its origins, development, and application in contemporary sociological research. To achieve this, several objectives were pursued, including a thorough exploration of the key concepts and theoretical frameworks underpinning Bourdieu's theory, a critical evaluation of its strengths and limitations, and the conduction of a social survey among students aged 18-21 to study the influence of the social environment on personality development.

The methodology employed in this study involved a multimodular approach, combining quantitative and qualitative methods. In particular, a survey was utilized to collect data on participants' opinions and beliefs regarding the impact of the environment on their habits, personality, and life. This method allowed for a deeper understanding of the role of the environment in shaping individual behavior, attitudes, and beliefs, in line with Bourdieu's theory of habitus and social space.

The findings from the critical analysis and survey revealed that habitus, as embodied cultural tendencies and practices, significantly influences an individual's perception of the world and their behavior within it. Bourdieu's concept of habitus is a product of long-term socialization within a specific socio-cultural environment, emphasizing the importance of social experience and upbringing in shaping one's habitus. Social space, on the other hand, comprises the structured and hierarchical positions and relationships within society, including factors such as class, gender, race, and cultural customs.

The social survey conducted among students provided valuable insights into the impact of habitus and social space on personality development, highlighting the diverse ways in which an individual's environment can affect their behavior, both positively and negatively. However, the research also underscored the importance of adopting a multimodal approach to examine the complex interplay between environment, habitus, and behavior.

In conclusion, the critical analysis of Bourdieu's theory of habitus and social space, along with the empirical findings from the social survey, contribute to the ongoing debate in the field of sociology. This study sheds light on the intricate relationship between social identity, cultural capital, social reproduction, and environmental relations as forms of power. The findings offer valuable information for future research and further enrich our understanding of the social forces that shape individuals and their behaviors.

References

1. Dr. Swartz D., Bourdieu's Theory of the State: A Critical Introduction.: "Stanford University Press", 2017.
2. Dr. Hayes G., Bourdieu and Social Movements: Ideological Struggles in the British Anti-Capitalist Movement.: "Ashgate Publishing", 2011.
3. Cerulo A. K., Identity Designs: The Sights and Sounds of a Nation.: "Rutgers University Press", 1995.
4. Dr. John R., The Habitus and Social Space Project, 2002.
5. Dr. Jeffrey A., The Practice of Cultural Sociology: Pierre Bourdieu's Habitus and the Social Space.: "Duke University Press", 2003.

INTERNATIONAL RANKINGS AND GLOBAL COMPETITION - CONSOLIDATING INTERNATIONAL PARTNERSHIPS

Amanzholov D.,

Student – Bachelor's degree – School of Informational Technologies

Niyazbek A.,

Student – Bachelor's degree – School of Informational Technologies

Mauletkhan N.,

Student – Bachelor's degree – School of Informational Technologies

Tileubayeva M.

KBTU, School of Natural and Social Sciences, PhD Doctor of Psychology

Abstract

This sociological project is dedicated to **international rankings and global competition**, their problems, as well as their solution – **consolidating international partnerships**. We have chosen this topic due to its high relevance.

Keywords: International rankings, global competition, international partnerships, consolidating international partnerships, cooperation, research, sustainability, responsibility, impacts of competition, global challenges, beneficial goals, hypothesis, education, social development, pandemic, innovation, efficiency, report, reviving and transforming human capital, the enabling environment and markets, survey, competitiveness.

INTRODUCTION

1.4. Overview: Relevance of the topic

International rankings and global competition are closely related and have become increasingly important in today's interconnected world. International rankings are assessments of countries or organizations based on a variety of factors such as economic strength, education, innovation, quality of life, and competitiveness. These rankings are often used by investors, businesses, and individuals to make decisions about where to invest, study, or live. Global competition refers to the competition between countries or organizations in the global marketplace. This competition can be fierce, as countries and organizations seek to attract investment, talent, and customers by offering competitive advantages such as lower costs, higher quality, or greater innovation.

1.5. Potential research questions

Here are some potential research questions and avenues to explore related to consolidating international partnerships within the context of international rankings and global competition:

IV. How do international rankings (e.g., World Bank's Ease of Doing Business Index, Global Competitiveness Index) affect the behavior of governments,

businesses, and other stakeholders in global competition?

V. What role do international partnerships (e.g., trade agreements, research collaborations, cross-border mergers and acquisitions) play in enhancing a country's global competitiveness?

VI. How do cultural differences and institutional factors (e.g., legal systems, and regulatory frameworks) affect the success of international partnerships?

IV. How can businesses and governments effectively balance the pursuit of global competitiveness with social and environmental responsibility?

These research questions could be approached through a variety of methods, such as case studies, surveys, experiments, and econometric analyses. The specific research design would depend on the research question and the availability of data and resources.

1.6. Defining the research problem

The problem addressed in this research is how international rankings affect global competition and how consolidating international partnerships can enhance a country's global competitiveness.

One problem with international rankings and global competition is that they can create a focus on short-term performance at the expense of long-term sustainability. For example, a country or organization